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The Establishment of Diplomatic Relations Between Cuba and the People's Republic of China (1960-1962)

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ABSTRACT

The following article examines the origins of diplomatic relations between Cuba and the People's Republic of China (P.R.C.), focusing on the period from 1960 to 1962, while discussing the facts that made the relationship possible in the context of the Cold War, and its implications. It also identifies the main similarities between the two countries, taking into account the ideas, the vision of the revolutionary processes, and the geopolitics. The objective of this work has been to describe and analyze the historical period to understand the reasons that led these two countries to establish formal relations beyond the founding of the revolutionary government in Cuba in 1959. At the same time, other aspects have been considered which influenced this process, such as the increasingly hostile relations between Cuba and the United States. In order to explain the facts, historical documents and articles related to the subject have been approached through a qualitative analysis, taking into consideration the diplomatic positions that both countries had with each other. This article argues that, while the P.R.C. was in a process of development of informal relations with the rest of the Latin American region –known as *People's Diplomacy*–, Cuba was the first Latin American country to establish formal relations with the Asian country, for which the bond between governments was much more direct. By the same token, it asserts that there was an agreement between them regarding ideas such as anti-imperialism and revolutionary methods, a meeting point which brought them closer even before the ideological component of communism.

Keywords

Cuba, People's Republic of China, Diplomatic Relations.

Introduction

The Cuban Revolution and the establishment of the Cuban government in 1959 were not only significant to the history of the island, but they also marked a turning point in the development of Latin American history. It brought about changes in the political, intellectual, and social movements of the region that affected both the territory itself and its relations with the world. For instance, the events that took place on the island led to the emergence of *New Left* movements in Latin America, influencing sectors that were not part of the traditional left. As a result, these inspired the guerrilla movements which ushered a new stage in the history of the region. Cuba became a prime example of how to gain power through guerrilla warfare. The possibility of radical change ignited new possibilities in areas that previously had no place. For this reason, the opportunity arose to forge new alliances and diplomatic relations.

In unison, the revolutionary process in Cuba changed not only its relationship with the United States, but also how the latter approached the rest of the Latin American region. Most of the region aligned with an anti-communist stance and joined the pro-Western capitalist blocs during the Cold War. The conflict that arose between Cuba and the U.S. influenced, among other things, the process through which Cuba would initiate formal relations with countries that no other Latin American state had established with before. Such is the case of the People's Republic of China (P.R.C.). In the early years of the P.R.C., due to the fact that most Latin American countries had not recognize it, the Asian country applied a policy known as *People's Diplomacy* or *people-to-people contact* not only with the aforementioned region but also with the rest of Asia and Africa, which consisted of informal establishment of links and the promotion of cultural and political exchange, put in practice through the sending and receiving of politicians and intellectuals¹.

Prior to the revolution, Cuba had been an example of the position of alignment with the United States, given that the successive governments that had existed until then—including that of dictator Fulgencio Batista—had been backed by the U.S., with which they had built a strong political and economic relationship. For this reason, until the rebels took power in Cuba, the island had been a supporter in the fight against communism and it had rejected links with any country which followed such ideology. Accordingly, Cuba had refused to maintain formal diplomatic relations with the P.R.C., much less recognize the new republic. However, this position would change after 1959.

As a result, this article focuses on the case of the People's Republic of China and its first formal diplomatic recognition in Latin America, observing how Cuba's situation and its enmity with the United States opened an opportunity for the Asian country in the region. This scenario marked the beginning of a new phase in the relations between Latin America and the People's Republic of China. Therefore, the first question that

¹ Jiang Shixue, "A New Look at the Chinese Relations with Latin America", *Nueva Sociedad*, (2005): 1-19.

arises focuses on the conditions that allowed the rapprochement between Cuba and the People's Republic of China and how this process came about. The second question revolves around understanding the first steps of the relationship between the two countries and what was the character and impact of such a connection. Finally, the third question focuses on what ideas and common goals they shared. Accordingly, the paper has been divided into three sections, all of which attempt to answer the formulated questions.

This topic is approached from a perspective which asserts that the rapprochement between China and Cuba is a result of a similar historical factor; that is, the concept of *revolution*. Although their revolutions occurred at different times and in different contexts, they allowed both Cuba and the P.R.C. to coincide in their ideas and visions of the world. Thus, it is relevant to take into account the ideas proposed by Hannah Arendt, who argues that “*violence is no more adequate to describe the phenomenon of revolution than change; only where change occurs in the sense of a new beginning, where violence is used to constitute an altogether different form of government, to bring about the formation of a new body politic, where the liberation from oppression aims at least at the constitution of freedom can we speak of revolution*”².

If we look at Cuba's international position after the guerrillas took power in 1959, we find a foreign policy based on three principles: “*anti-imperialism: internationalism, solidarity and cooperation; and respect for contemporary Public International Law*”³. Regarding the P.R.C., its position during the early years after the establishment of the revolutionary government in 1949 was based on the international policy ideas of Mao Zedong of *leaning to one side*. With the consolidation of the P.R.C. as of 1954, the Asian country sought to achieve an international position adequate for its interests –for instance the maintenance of its sovereignty and the existence of the country. This was in the course of a historical moment of conflict with a power like the United States, which wanted to contain the advance of communism in Asia, and the differences with the U.S.S.R. after the 20th congress in 1956, with its guidelines that would open the door to discrepancies, leading to the Sino-Soviet dispute from 1958⁴.

In terms of the methodology, through the analysis of documents and articles which focus on the establishment of diplomatic relations between Cuba and the P.R.C. between 1960 and 1962, it is possible to observe aspects such as the realization of the first diplomatic steps, the importance of the roots of their link as well as shared ideas and strategic visions. Therefore, the emphasis is put on the origin of their relationship during the existence of a bipolar world marked by the Cold War, in which both countries were in need of allies. For the P.R.C, such bond entailed obtaining a formal gateway to Latin America that went beyond

² Hannah Arendt, *On Revolution*, (London: Penguin Group, 1990): 35.

³ Isabel Allende Karam. "La política exterior de la Revolución cubana: Una mirada sobre la política exterior de la Revolución Cubana y las dimensiones de su universalidad." In *Cuba en revolución*, by Luis Suárez Salazar, 105-128. Buenos Aires: CLACSO, 2019.

⁴ Eugenio Anguiano. “Diplomacia de la República Popular China”, in *China contemporánea*, by Eugenio Anguiano, Flora Botton Beja, Romer Alejandro Cornejo and Ma. Teresa Rodríguez (El Colegio de Mexico, 2001), 179-284.

people-to-people diplomacy; while for Cuba, the P.R.C. became a potential ally outside the Soviet bloc, in an increasingly complicated situation with the U.S.

The establishment of diplomatic relations

During the first years after the installment of the People's Republic of China in 1949, the Latin American region joined the standpoint of not acknowledging the newly formed state. The absence of formal relations between the P.R.C. and certain countries in the world, including the Latin American countries, led to the search for alternative methods of connection, which would allow it to gain allies in such a distant and diverse region, either by initiating ties or friendships through organizations or by starting rapprochements with influential people from political or intellectual circles. China's ties with other countries were important to its interests, as diplomatic relations are an important mechanism that derives in state recognition, and prosperity as a result of exchanges.

Hence, the Asian country developed a strategy regarded as *people-to-people contact*, which implied that countries –among them Latin American ones –maintained cooperation links in cultural, academic, or ideological areas. This entailed that the friendships could be forged through other mechanisms which went beyond government-to-government relations. It is estimated that between 1950 and 1959 approximately 1,200 artists, trade unionists, merchants, and intellectuals from Latin America visited the P.R.C.; therefore, this policy intended to gradually bring the countries closer together, for the purpose of establishing diplomatic relations in the future⁵. The idea was to strengthen friendships directly with the people coming from those countries where the governments had not recognize the P.R.C. and, in this way, the Asian country built alliances, and transmitted ideas beyond the formal diplomatic barriers.

In terms of the leftist political parties in Latin America, by 1959 –ten years after the creation of the People's Republic of China– the majority of the communist parties in Latin America mostly followed the lines and political-ideological dictates of the Soviet Union. These precepts were far from the ideas followed by the P.R.C., which was committed to the revolution, as opposed to the general guidelines of *peaceful coexistence*. This reflected the consequences of the distancing of the Asian country from the U.S.S.R. due to the revisionist stance initiated and adopted by Nikita Khrushchev's government. In some cases, it produced the fragmentation of Latin American Marxist-Leninist organizations that were divided between those which followed Chinese communism and those which continued being committed to Soviet communism⁶. This situation also

⁵ Xu Shicheng, "Las diferentes etapas de las relaciones sino-latinoamericanas." *Nueva Sociedad*, 2006: 102-113.

⁶ Miguel Ángel Urrego, "Historia del Maoísmo en América Latina: entre la lucha armada y servir al pueblo", *Anuario Colombiano de Historia Social y de la Cultura*, (2017): 111-135.

encouraged the P.R.C. to expand its contacts beyond the ideological component and attract different influential personalities from Latin America, which didn't necessarily come from communist parties.

As a result, such state of affairs influenced the way events unfolded when the Cuban revolutionaries took power in 1959, providing possibilities for the Asian country to approach the island through a diplomatic friendship. Therefore, their rapprochement was a consequence of the political and governmental change in Cuba, as well as the revolutionary actions that put a halt to U.S. interference. The new Cuban government yearned for a foreign policy that would benefit its interests, and it consequently searched for links with those countries that would allow economic agreements and could support its political process. On September 2nd, 1960, Fidel Castro declared the rupture of ties with Taiwan, a process that eventually materialized on September 28th of the same year, thus establishing diplomatic relations with the P.R.C. and recognizing it as the only government of China. Formal relations allowed for dialogue and friendship between the two governments, enabling the beginning of a new chapter in the history of the Asian country's relationship with Latin America. In practice, the relationship involved China's backing to the aspirations of the Cuban revolution, agreements of trade exchanges through goods and services, Cuba's support to the P.R.C. establishing its representativeness as a state in the United Nations, and settlements for academic cooperation in science, technology, research, education, sports, and tourism. Consequently, Chinese students went to Cuba to learn Spanish and train as experts on Latin American issues⁷. An example of this was prestigious Chinese intellectual Xu Shicheng, who took part in the relations between the Asian country and Cuba during his youth in the 1960s.

In this sense, Cuba was the first Latin American country to establish diplomatic relations with China, and therefore to recognize its sovereignty and state. At the same time, the way geopolitics developed in Latin America was also modified. Diplomatic relations between Cuba and the P.R.C. exposed the departure of the island from the international politics of the rest of Latin America. It is possible to observe here how the aspirations of two countries coincided, which shared a common ground beyond cultural differences or geographical distances, particularly in terms of the fight against imperialism. In this sense, there were clear demonstrations from the side of the Asian country in support of Cuba in its conflicts with the United States⁸. The change in power produced in Cuba in 1959 and its distancing from the U.S. arose as an opportunity for countries like the P.R.C. to diplomatically approach the governments of Latin America. For this reason, it could be understood as a positive sign in order to give prestige to the new Cuban government and encourage the follow-up of this process in other countries of the region during the following decades.

⁷ Mao Xianglin, Adrian H. Hearn, and Liu Weiguang, "China and Cuba: 160 Years and Looking Ahead", *Latin American Perspectives*, 42, no. 6 (November 2015): 140-152.

⁸ Jiang Shixue, "A New Look at the Chinese Relations with Latin America", *Nueva Sociedad*, (2005): 1-19

In February 1960, Chinese Foreign Minister Chen Yi had communicated a message in favor of the revolutionary processes in Cuba, observing the events as a new beginning for Latin American liberation⁹. The concepts of "nationality and democracy" were the slogan, highlighted both in the P.R.C. and in Cuba, which were central to the relation between the two. As a way to reinforce this concept, we can ponder the words of president of the China-Latin America Friendship Association, Chu Tu'nan, who praised "*the vigorous development of national and democratic movements in Latin America*"¹⁰ and also argued that "*owing to the ever-increasing strength of the socialist camp and the vigorous development of the national and democratic movements in Africa, Asia and Latin America, U.S. imperialism has become isolated*"¹¹. Thus, the United States undoubtedly becomes, while considering the content of the concepts, the common adversary. At that juncture, there could be doubts about the course of the Cuban revolutionary government and also about whether it was close to socialism or not, but what was evident to China was its increasing dispute with the U.S. and its methods to overthrow the government of the island.

In this sense, the Cuban revolution propitiated the rapprochement between the P.R.C. and the island, as a result of its nationalist and democratic character. This produced a shift in the scope of reach of the P.R.C. in Latin America, since from then on it was able to strengthen relations with country of that region that went beyond *people-to-people* contact, now based on a diplomatic friendship. At the same time, the notion that they shared a common enemy, the United States, would also enable deeper ties between them. Although at the onset of the new Cuban government the P.R.C. debated whether the revolution was Marxist-Leninist or if it would take that path, it highly praised the island's anti-imperialist character and its quest for independence, features that will be deepened later on.

First steps in the diplomatic relations

As a way to exemplify how the first stage in the establishment of the diplomatic relations between Cuba and the P.R.C. developed, it is noteworthy to highlight the celebration in 1960 of the anniversary of the Cuban revolution and the Latin American independence in the Asian country, which suggested a political signal in favor of the island and the radical processes that developed in the region. In an article published in the People's Daily of China, it is stated that Chu Tu'nan explained the reasons why both countries should join forces, stressing that "*the peoples of Latin America have waged continuous and heroic struggles against U.S.*

⁹ Marisela Connelly and Romer Cornejo Bustamante, *China- América Latina: Génesis y desarrollo de su relación*, (Ciudad de México: El Colegio de México, 1992).

¹⁰ Peking Review, III, 35, of August 30, 1960, in Ernst Halperin, *Peking and The Latin America Communists*, (Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Center for International Studies, 1966), 2.

¹¹ Peking Review, III, 37, September 14, 1960, in Ernst Halperin, *Peking and The Latin America Communists*, (Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Center for International Studies, 1966), 3.

imperialism for nearly a century. He particularly pointed out that under the leadership of the Cuban Revolutionary Government headed by Prime Minister Castro, the Cuban people have achieved great victories in the national democratic revolution, thus pushing the people's anti-imperialist struggle in Latin America to a new stage, which is a great success for Latin America. The struggle of the people of all countries against U.S. imperialism has set a glorious example and has made great contributions to the struggle of the people of the world against the aggressive and war policies of U.S. imperialism and the defense of world peace (...) He specifically pointed out that under the leadership of the Cuban Revolutionary Government headed by Prime Minister Castro, the Cuban people have achieved great victories in the national democratic revolution, thus pushing the anti-imperialist struggle of the peoples of Latin America to a new stage, which is for Latin America. The struggle of the people of all countries against U.S. imperialism has set a glorious example and has made great contributions to the struggle of the people of the world against U.S. imperialism's aggressive and war policies and defending world peace"¹².

Therefore, we can argue that the first steps of the relationship between the P.R.C. and Cuba were characterized by a common agreement on the imperialist character of the United States and the importance of the unity in Latin America to defeat it. The P.R.C. criticized U.S. leverage over Latin America, calling this influence an "imperialist subjugation" of the region and emphasizing that Latin America had faced the interference of England after Spanish and Portuguese colonialism and that of the United States after its defeat. The Asian country argued that the subjugation of the Latin American region was detrimental since it implied undergoing misery and human exploitation.

If we take into account what has been exposed so far, we can comprehend that the P.R.C. observed the Latin American events of the 1960s as a long-term historical process. While analyzing how imperialism had affected Latin America, this analysis shed light not only on the process of struggle against the United States, but also the antecedents of such development, taking into consideration the region's search for independence from Europe. Thus, such history shared similarities with China. In this sense, the PRC's arguments coincide with those of Fidel Castro, who referred to guerrillas as a means to achieve the independence that Cuba had been yearning for since the colonial period under the rule of Spain. This is one of the greatest points of contact

¹² “拉丁美洲各国人民近百年来对美帝国主义开展了持续不断的英勇斗争。他特别指出，古巴人民在以卡斯特罗总理为首的古巴革命政府的领导下，取得了民族民主革命的伟大胜利，从而把拉丁美洲各国人民反帝斗争推进到一个新的阶段，为拉丁美洲各国人民反对帝国主义的斗争树立了光辉的榜样，对世界人民反对帝国主义的侵略政策、战争政策，保卫世界和平的斗争作出了巨大贡献(。。)他特别指出，古巴人民在以卡斯特罗总理为首的古巴革命政府的领导下，取得了民族民主革命的伟大胜利，从而把拉丁美洲各国人民反帝斗争推进到一个新的阶段，为拉丁美洲各国人民反对帝国主义的斗争树立了光辉的榜样，对世界人民反对帝国主义的侵略政策、战争政策，保卫世界和平的斗争作出了巨大贡献”。“祝独立民主的拉丁美洲从斗争烈火中诞生。首都盛会纪念拉丁美洲各国争取民族独立150周年、庆祝古巴革命胜利二周年”人民日报1960年12月27日 第1版 (“Wish independent and democratic Latin America emerge from the flames of struggle. The capital event commemorates the 150th anniversary of the struggle for national independence of Latin American countries and celebrates the second anniversary of the victory of the Cuban Revolution”. [People's Daily, December 27, 1960, the first 1 edition]).

between Cuba and China as the first steps in their diplomatic relations. It even took place before any ideological convergence, for example, socialism, which Cuba adopted in 1961. Both countries found common ground and interests that led them to friendship and a good relationship.

Relations between the two countries began to deepen in various areas thanks to bilateral agreements. Thus, a branch of the Chinese media company Xinhua, which had been established in Havana in April 1959, became the first representation of the Asian country in Cuba and also in Latin America, serving several purposes from then on¹³. This ensured that information coming from the P.R.C. reached Latin America, creating a novel source for the dissemination of ideas and news in the region, and allowing a different path in the ways of analysis, influencing the Latin American worldview. It also made it possible to obtain information about the other's situation more quickly and directly, because normally news about what was happening in China or vice versa could only be obtained through third parties or with the help of people who had contacts with the Chinese. From this point of view, it is interesting to highlight that the establishment of the Chinese media in Cuba was an important step to spread information faster and more efficiently. On the one hand, China possessed a medium that informed it of Latin American realities, and on the other hand, it allowed the transmission of events that took place in Asia, as well as ideas and reflections. Cuba was a strategic point because it was located in Latin America, but also because of its proximity to the United States. From there, it was important to have a means of communication that was so geographically distant.

In addition to the exchange of ideas and information, the consolidation and security of the relationship between the two countries was grounded in an economic agreement. For this reason, trade was not only something desirable but also something necessary for both states. In this sense, events such as the one in November 1960, when Ernesto *Che* Guevara visited China in order to achieve economic cooperation, became of utmost relevance. This issue was of central importance for Cuba, which considered these agreements as something fundamental to maintain the development of the revolution and the scope of its plans. The economic aspect gained importance due to the deterioration of relations with the United States, which until then had been the main source of foreign exchange and goods for Cuba. The island's hostile relations with the U.S. had consequences that hit the Cuban economy hard. Prior to meetings with P.R.C. leaders, Guevara referred to the problems Cuba had with the United States, which he considered an imperialist country that attacked both the island and China. Consequently, the two countries reached an understanding along these lines. The alliance aimed at helping to preserve the sovereignty of both countries, for which they reached an agreement on the financing and purchase of sugar from Cuba¹⁴.

¹³ Marisela Connelly and Bustamante Romer Cornejo, *China- América Latina: Génesis y desarrollo de su relación*, (Ciudad de México: El Colegio de México, 1992).

¹⁴ *Ib.*

Strategically, the rapprochement between the P.R.C. and Cuba was an alternative in the search for links that would benefit the continuity of the revolutionary process and its defense against the problems with its North American neighbor. The island's alliance with the Asian country was important in order to obtain resources through economic exchanges while seeking mechanisms that would support the development process. For China, Cuba was the first country that allowed it to establish itself diplomatically in the Latin American region. The Cuban Revolution enabled formal relations that improved not only through exchanges, but also through the opportunity to connect with countries in a region like Latin America.

To sum up, the first steps of the relationship between Cuba and the P.R.C. were built in the grounds of the value of Cuba as a representative of the Latin American historical struggle against imperialism, and in the cultural and economic exchange that resulted from their mutual understanding. The bilateral connection was a transcendental event for both, due to the fact that for any independent country, to obtain as much diplomatic recognition as possible in the world becomes of utmost importance in order to secure its existence in the international community. For the Asian country this meant its first recognition by a Latin American country, for which it implied expanding the borders of countries diplomatically linked, at times when the majority of the region rejected the Asian country. The Caribbean country became an opportunity for the P.R.C. to go beyond the diplomacy of interpersonal contacts and establish official relations with a Latin American country. At the level of international organizations, the P.R.C. found an ally in Cuba, which supported its application for admission to the United Nations. For the island, these agreements were a possibility to ease economic problems that could arise from the attacks and intrusions of the United States in its territory.

Common ideas and themes

As observed above, it is possible to view that in the first stage of their relationship, the P.R.C. valued the Cuban revolution as a nationalist process in pursuit of democracy. When the diplomatic relationship between them was settled, Cuba was not cataloged as a socialist ally but as an anti-imperialist one. Hence, certain shared values were accentuated, such as the search for freedom, independence, sovereignty, and self-determination. *“The Chinese and the Soviets were skeptical because, according to the Marxist-Leninist canons, the seizure of power and the stages and characteristics of the revolution were not the usual ones. They had to meditate for some time before accepting Castro's claim. The Chinese, without yet recognizing the socialist character of the Cuban Revolution, continued to give it their moral support”*¹⁵.

¹⁵ *“Los chinos y los soviéticos se mostraron escépticos porque, de acuerdo con los cánones marxista-leninistas, la toma del poder y las etapas y características de la revolución no eran las acostumbradas. Tuvieron que meditar algún tiempo antes de aceptar la afirmación de Castro. Los chinos, sin reconocer aún el carácter socialista de la Revolución Cubana, continuaron dándole su apoyo moral”*, obtained from *Guangming Ribao*, 29 de septiembre de 1960, 4, in Marisela Connelly and Bustamante Romer Cornejo, *China- América Latina: Génesis y desarrollo de su relación*, (Ciudad de México: El Colegio de México, 1992), 66.

As soon as Cuba declared its orientation towards socialism in 1961, China adopted a cautious attitude since international communism initially defined the Cuban revolution as democratic and bourgeois. It was President Liu Shaoqi who recognized through his speech in China in September 1961 that the island had opted for socialist development and later, in July 1962, he reaffirmed that after a nationalist and democratic process, Cuba had become the first socialist country in Latin America¹⁶.

As an important contribution later on, in an interview conducted by the Uruguayan writer and journalist Eduardo Galeano in 1963, Prime Minister Zhou Enlai would affirm that “*If a country wants to make the socialist revolution, it must accept the principles of Marxism-Leninism. And Marxism-Leninism cannot be monopolized by the Communist Party. Any revolutionary can have this weapon. When Fidel Castro conquered victory through armed struggle, he was not a member of the Communist Party*”¹⁷. From this perspective, it is understood that China's position in the matter was that beyond the fact that the Cuban revolution had not been led by from the Communist Party, it had oriented towards Marxism-Leninism in its development. From this premise Cuba was seen as a socialist country from 1961 since it accepted the guiding principles of this ideology. In relation with the ideas above, it is possible to define the conceptions that governed the friendship between Cuba and the P.R.C. at that time: that the actions carried out by the national and democratic revolutions could only be overcome by adopting a socialist model¹⁸.

We can also detect one more point in common between the two countries in how the P.R.C. agreed with the model of guerrilla executed in Cuba, cataloging it as a suitable prototype for other Latin American countries that also sought freedom. It therefore became the recommended methodology to accomplish national democratic revolution. This was stated by Premier Zhou Enlai at a banquet in honor of *Che* Guevara's visit to China in November of 1960, who praised the process experienced on the island¹⁹. Thus, Cuba was also seen as a potential ally to display the ideals of Chinese communism in Latin America. Up until that moment, the region had not been a priority for the Asian country, given that from a geopolitical point of view the Latin American territory was the third world region farthest from China; it conversely reached some magnitude after 1960. Latin America was commonly seen as the *backyard* of the United States, so its emancipation could be perceived as a severe setback to imperialism. For that reason, during this period attention was paid to the ideas of the revolutionary leader Ernesto *Che* Guevara (whose texts and speeches were translated into Chinese),

¹⁶ Marisela Connelly and Bustamante Romer Cornejo, *China- América Latina: Génesis y desarrollo de su relación*, (Ciudad de México: El Colegio de México, 1992).

¹⁷ “*Si un país quiere hacer la revolución socialista, debe aceptar los principios revolucionarios del marxismo-leninismo. Y el marxismo-leninismo no puede ser monopolizado por el Partido Comunista. Cualquier revolucionario puede disponer de esta arma. Cuando Fidel Castro conquistó la victoria por medio de la lucha armada, no era miembro del Partido Comunista*”. Eduardo Galeano, *China 1964. Crónica de un desafío*, (Bs. As: Jorge Alvarez Editor, 1964), 161.

¹⁸ Chinese Central Committee on the Moscow November 1960 meeting of Communist parties, which was passed on January 18, 1961, *Peking Review*, IV, 4, January 27, 1961, in Ernst Halperin, *Peking and the Latin American Communists*, (Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for International Studies, International Communism Project, 1966).

¹⁹ William E. Ratliff, “Communist China and Latin America, 1949-1972”, *Asian Survey* 12, no. 10 (1972): 846-863.

who proposed a radical alternative through revolution as a means to achieve power, which altogether differed from the Soviet revisionist approach of the time –with which China disagreed–²⁰.

As mentioned above, just as Cuba and the P.R.C. began their relationship in 1960, a common adversary also flourished: imperialism, which both countries opposed; such concept was not only a proclamation or a theoretical definition, because they gave it a name, and that was the United States. The consensus was not only regarding a common enemy but also in the way to face it; thus, the revolutionary action acquired an important relevance in the relations between Cuba and the P.R.C. The Asian country stated that it longed for *an independent, free, democratic, and happy Latin America*²¹. With this, it understood that the path traced by the Cuban rebels in *Sierra Maestra* was the suitable one.

The aforementioned president of the China-Latin America Friendship Association Chu Tu'nan described in 1960 the actions of the United States as that of a country which had not yet reconciled with the notion of having been defeated in the search to dominate Cuba, and was therefore strongly hostile through attacks, economic blockade, embargos against the island, and the increase in the shipment of troops to the Caribbean Sea to complete an armed intervention. China criticized how the North American country used the O.A.S. –which also dominated– to separate Cuba from the rest of the Latin American countries, making them hostile to the Cuban revolution. At the same time, the Chinese people knew perfectly well the complexity of confronting U.S. imperialism; they had experienced it in the past and did so again in the 1960s, resisting its attempts to influence Asia. That is why they saw Cuba as an ally to confront the hegemony of a world power like the United States²². *“From the victory and continuous development of the Cuban revolution, the peoples of Latin American countries will also find the right way to get rid of the enslavement and control of US imperialism and achieve complete national liberation. Of course, the struggle in the future will be tortuous, complicated, and arduous. U.S. imperialism will also use new conspiracies and tricks. As Chairman Mao Zedong pointed out, “troubleshoot, fail, make trouble again, and fail again until it perishes.” The logic of imperialism and all reactionaries in the world towards the cause of the people will never go against this logic.” As long as the people of the Latin American countries strengthen their unity and persist in their struggle, the US imperialist policy of aggression and war will surely fail. U.S. imperialism will certainly not escape the shameful failure of the Spanish and Portuguese colonial rulers in the Latin American countries*²³.

²⁰ *Ib.*

²¹ “祝独立民主的拉丁美洲从斗争烈火中诞生. 首都盛会纪念拉丁美洲各国争取民族独立 150 周年、庆祝古巴革命胜利二周年”人民日报1960年12月27日 第1版 (*“Wish independent and democratic Latin America emerge from the flames of struggle. The capital event commemorates the 150th anniversary of the struggle for national independence of Latin American countries and celebrates the second anniversary of the victory of the Cuban Revolution”*). [People's Daily, December 27, 1960, the first 1 edition].

²² *Ib.*

²³拉丁美洲各国人民也将从古巴革命的胜利和不断发展中, 找到摆脱美帝国主义奴役和控制和实现彻底的民族解放的正确道路。当然, 今后的斗争还会是曲折、复杂和艰巨的, 美帝国主义还会施展新的阴谋诡计, 正如毛泽东主席所指出的, “捣乱, 失败, 再捣乱, 再失败, 直至灭亡——这就是帝国主义和世界上一切反动派对待人民事业的逻辑, 他们决

During the meeting between the Cuban leader Fidel Castro and the Chinese ambassador, Shen Jian in 1961, the former formulated that Latin America hosted great transformations and that the problems Cuba had to face were somewhat similar to those of China. The island was being held responsible for every revolution that occurred on the American continent; in this sense, the Chinese ambassador stated: *“This is very important. There is much in common between the Cuban revolution and the Chinese revolution, therefore there will be similarities in the problems that we encounter and face. What you said is exactly our situation in Asia. China will be blamed for every revolution that happens in an Asian country. We don't mind these kinds of accusations. [After all,] the people will make the revolution [sooner or later]. It is good that people rise and make the revolution”*²⁴. At the same meeting, Castro argued that U.S. President John F. Kennedy exhibited an aggressive attitude towards Cuba, highlighting that on the one hand, the U.S. wanted to win the sympathy of Latin America, and on the other, it was attacking countries like Cuba, without financially solving the problems in the countries of the region. Hereafter, the Chinese representative added that the U.S. had financed Kuomintang leader Chiang Kai-shek during his confrontation with the Chinese Communist Party²⁵, which strengthened the idea that both countries had similar difficulties. The vision that Cuba and China shared is reflected in this conversation, in terms of the similarities in their revolutionary processes –beyond the ideological distances –in the face of imperialist interference, and the challenges in the trajectories that provided them with lessons learned. The conclusion they both reached was that, in modern history, China had struck the first blow to the United States, and that Cuba had executed the second one.

Likewise, before a Cuban cultural delegation in China in 1961, Chairman Mao Zedong expressed his full support for the revolutionary cause against the United States and criticized those countries which, without being imperialists, succumbed to it: *“China and Cuba are two friendly countries. We help and support each other. Our goal is one. Oppose imperialism. American imperialism is the largest imperialism. It does not only oppress us, but it also oppresses you. It oppresses people all over the world. In some non-imperialist countries, there are some imperialist running dogs. We must oppose not only imperialism but also imperialist running dogs”*²⁶. Chinese support for Cuba against the U.S. was reflected on several occasions; for example, in *Peking*

不会违背这个逻辑的”。只要拉丁美洲各国人民加强团结，坚持斗争，美帝国主义的侵略政策和战争政策必将彻底失败。“美帝国主义一定逃不出西班牙和葡萄牙殖民统治者在拉丁美洲各国所走的可耻的失败的道路”。人民日报1960年12月27日 第4版 (“US imperialism cannot escape the old road defeat colonialism. Cuba has set a shining example for the victory of the revolution in Latin America”. [People's Daily, December 27, 1960, the first 4 edition])

²⁴Ambassador Shen Jian “Cable from the Chinese Embassy in Cuba, 'Memorandum of Conversation between China's Ambassador to Cuba, Shen Jian, and Cuban Prime Minister Fidel Castro',” February 11, 1961, History and Public Policy Program Digital Archive, PRC FMA 111-00612-01,4-11. Translated by Zhang Qian. <http://digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org/document/115153>.

²⁵ *Ib.*

²⁶“中和古巴是友好的家，我相互助，相互支持。我的目是一。反帝主。美帝主是帝主中最大的一，它不但迫我，也迫你，它迫全世界人民。在一些不是帝主的家中，都有一些帝主的走狗。我不但要反帝主，也要反帝主的走狗。”“Conversation from [Mao Zedong's] Audience with a Cuban Cultural Delegation,” April 19, 1961, History and Public Policy Program Digital Archive, Gang er si Wuhan daxue zongbu et al, eds., Mao Zedong sixiang wansui (Long Live Mao Zedong Thought), vol. 5 (1961-1968) (Wuhan, internal circulation, May 1968): 8. <https://digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org/document/240155>

Review magazine, on April 21, 1961, a special supplement mentioned how the Kennedy administration threatened world peace and attacked democratic processes in Latin America, highlighting that Cuba had the full support of the P.R.C. and the socialist camp, and also arguing that efforts had to be gathered in order to defend the Caribbean country from the attack of imperialism²⁷. When the missile crisis conflict broke down in 1962, China supported Cuba through popular demonstrations in the Asian country. This is interpreted by some analyzes as a way to seek greater proximity between both countries in the face of the dispute the P.R.C. had with the U.S.S.R.²⁸.

The diplomatic ties between China and Cuba proved significant because of the dichotomy between the island and the United States, but also for the international policy adopted by the U.S.S.R. at that time. Their friendship entailed building a link with a communist country other than the Soviet Union and its guidelines, which was not entirely convenient for the Soviets either due to their divergence with China. It seems that the policy of *peaceful coexistence* carried out by the U.S.S.R was seen by China as surrender to imperialism that fundamentally affected countries like Cuba. In this sense, we can observe that the aid of the P.R.C. to Cuba competed with the Soviet aid. The differences were exposed when the Asian country sought a more active fight against imperialism and in this way helped the liberation of the subjugated countries, which led to its support for Cuba when the North American invasion of the Bay of Pigs took place. China also provided support to Cuba during the missile crisis occurred after the U.S.S.R. had negotiated with the United States whereas overlooking the participation of the island in the matter, an action that the Chinese government emphatically criticized²⁹.

Despite the geographical and cultural distances, the way both the P.R.C. and Cuba observed social processes and the world as a whole in this first stage pushed them into becoming allies. However, while in their positions there were many commonalities, they also generated different perceptions in how they viewed their relationship. In the abovementioned meeting between Fidel Castro and Ambassador Shen Jian in 1961, it was argued that while China emphasized that the friendship was better characterized as mutual aid through which both nations benefited, *Che* Guevara referred to it as a relationship of selfless help and assistance. For Cuba, the Asian country's aid was seen as modest but significant on a symbolic level in the face of the danger of U.S. invasion. Both appealed to internationalism as a way to unite the efforts of the countries that fought against imperialism³⁰. Thus, Ambassador Shen Jian maintained that “*Cuba is revolutionary, and China is also*

²⁷ Peking Review, 16, April 21st, 1961.

²⁸ Eugenio Anguiano, “Diplomacy of the People's Republic of China”, in *Contemporary China*, by Eugenio Anguiano, Flora Botton Beja, Romer Alejandro Cornejo and Ma. Teresa Rodríguez, (The College of Mexico, 2001), 179-284.

²⁹ Ernst Halperin, *Peking and the Latin American Communists*, (Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for International Studies, International Communism Project, 1966).

³⁰ Ambassador Shen Jian “Cable from the Chinese Embassy in Cuba, 'Memorandum of Conversation between China's Ambassador to Cuba, Shen Jian, and Cuban Prime Minister Fidel Castro',” February 11, 1961, History and Public Policy Program Digital Archive, PRC FMA 111-00612-01,4-11. Translated by Zhang Qian.<http://digitalarchive.wilsoncenter.org/document/115153>

revolutionary. The success of the Chinese revolution was several years before that of Cuba, therefore [we have] a duty to support the Cuban revolution. Since the success of the revolution was several years later than that of China, Cuba also has the right to demand help from the countries that were successful before. This is internationalism"³¹.

To sum up, the two countries shared political values and principles such as anti-imperialism and democratic national liberation. Beyond the true scope of material support capabilities, the closeness that Cuba built with the P.R.C. began thanks to the objectives and ideas shared by the political leaders of both countries. This was a product of the international situation and the fact that China had experienced many of the same challenges that Cuba did in its own revolution. Likewise, the ideas that the Cuban and Chinese leaders expressed had as a pretext the search for freedom and social justice. However, in the face of the conflict between the P.R.C. and the U.S.S.R., Cuba would strengthen ties with the latter, causing the relationship with the Asian country to decline in the second half of the 1960s.

Conclusion

It is important to observe how Cuba developed links with socialist countries that were not under the influence of the U.S.S.R. In the case of the P.R.C., relations were based on coincidences of ideas and values such as those of national revolution and anti-imperialism. Although the alliance with China will have its setbacks in the future, the period dealt with in this article shows how Cuba was the first Latin American country to establish formal diplomatic relations with China, and it also portrays the characteristics and components of that relationship. Cuba became, for the Asian country, the gateway to Latin America. During the first years, cultural and political exchanges were the main characteristic in their link: Chinese news agencies were opened in Cuba and the exchange of products was agreed upon. These ties were born as a way for the two countries to cooperate and obtain mutual benefits in the face of the complex situation of the Cold War.

For Cuba, China represented both an important partner in the conflict with the United States and a possibility of friendship with another non-Western country with which it shared similarities in ideals and objectives on a historical level. The independence process as well as the government of the Cuban revolution could only be maintained if the island managed to defend itself militarily and develop its economy to improve its population's lives. At the same time, when much of the Western world –influenced by the U.S. – sought to isolate Cuba, the Latin American country needed to establish political and commercial relations with those

³¹ *Ib.*

outside the influence of the United States; therefore it had to look for all possible alternatives, even beyond the U.S.S.R.

Another aspect worth highlighting is that the links between China and Cuba arise outside of Marxist-Leninist ideology. However, this does not mean that the importance that this ideology had and has in the relations between these two countries is excluded. If we approach the subject from a historical and empirical perspective, we can note that the Caribbean country's road to socialism was officially adopted as of April 16, 1961, that is, after the beginning of formal relations with China, and that the island was not recognized as socialist by the Asian country until September 1961. Thus, when the rapprochement began, they coincided in the ideas of national democratic revolution and anti-imperialism, as well as in the struggle against the United States. The latter was perceived by both China and Cuba as an empire that threatened their independence. When Cuba began to follow the path of Marxism-Leninism, relations with China were put on a different level, since they shared the same ideology. In summary, in the alliance and friendship between the two countries, the national revolution and anti-imperialism were points of agreement even before the socialist ideology.

Finally, it is important to clarify that Fidel Castro will distance himself from the P.R.C. in the second half of the 1960s. Both the U.S.S.R. and China had had a relationship with the island, and their ability to support it during its difficult times with the United States had differed. The Sino-Soviet dispute had an impact on Cuba, so much so that later, in 1965, Cuba turned away from Beijing and focused on its alliance with Moscow. These facts, however, do not diminish the importance of the common ground and similar causes that united China and Cuba and initiated a relationship that can be considered the first rapprochement in the history of the link between the two countries.

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